

Department of Information and Computing Sciences

Effect of neural network design on lagrangian ocean modelling uncertainty

Master Thesis

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Abstract

Physicists have access to Lagrangian ocean models to predict particle densities, where they have certain sets of parameters which they can change to alter the simulation results. The issue with it is that these simulations are fixed. They will not vary every time they run their models, so the question of having uncertainty measurements is not possible. To have some form of uncertainty measurements in the prediction of particle densities, we explore the use of multi-headed Convolutional LSTM (ConvLSTM) for forecasting particle densities and present the network's confidence in its predictions. We make use of Bayesian approximation techniques to do so. We train and test our network on data generated by Lagrangian ocean simulators. We investigate how different design choices of the network effect the confidence of the model's predictions. Our experiments show that while the network has struggled with the output accuracy, it represents its shortcomings in its confidence measurements.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Lagrangian particle simulations are used to model fluid behavior and the motion of tracers in the fluid. A practical example of this is the simulation of microplastics in the ocean as particles. Lagrangian simulators, such as parcels [8], follow a mechanistic modelling approach [24], i.e. if provided with the same simulation parameters, the output will be the same, meaning there would be no variation in the simulation results. Changing the simulation parameters results in different datasets. In an ideal world, each of the scenarios generated by varying the parameters can be deemed correct. There is no way to decide whether one scenario has a higher probability of occurrence than the other.

In this research, we aim to find a way where our deep learning network can learn the underlying mechanism of Lagrangian simulations. We then apply the trained knowledge by forecasting the simulation for certain timesteps, and provide the decision makers with the level of confidence in the forecasts, so that they know how much to rely upon the results. In our project we will be forecasting particle densities.

In order to provide a confidence measure to the forecast, the prediction technique needs to be probabilistic. Most pattern recognition and replication techniques are inherently probabilistic, in contrast to the mechanistic Lagrangian simulation framework, as they consume different equally probable input datasets to provide predictions of varying certainty. In our project, the input data to the pattern replication engine are the many equally probable results of the Lagrangian simulation scenarios. Our project employs neural network (NN) and deep learning methods because of their demonstrated prowess to learn intricate patterns in various fields such as image recognition [16], weather forecasting [11] and others. Problems that come with modeling fluid dynamics are different from those mentioned. In order to analyze fluid flows, it is often necessary to quantify its underlying mechanism. Recent progress for NNs in fluid dynamics has been very promising. NN architectures have an input layer which takes in the data and then gives a prediction using the output layer. Nonlinear optimization methods, such as backpropagation [19], minimize the error between the prediction and the training data by identifying the network weights.

To add credence to our objective, i.e. to quantify uncertainty, NNs inherently try to match the target pattern as best as possible, averaged over the whole training set, by minimizing the optimization metric, i.e., the objective function. Therefore, when predicting the output for previously unseen input, the network not only provides the prediction but also its deviation from the mean, i.e. the prediction error. This prediction error, for example MSE, demonstrates the stochastic nature of neural network predictions. In our project, we look towards Bayesian inference. The fact that every ML framework can be converted into a Bayesian framework [4] makes it highly adaptable. In this research, we want to observe how changing certain design choices effects the network's confidence on its output. Formally put, we want to provide answers to the following research question:

How do the neural networks co-estimate particle densities and their uncertainty and how changing certain network design choices effect the prediction?

Tackeling uncertain particle estimation is relevant to our specific application of ocean plastic pollution. Every year more and more plastic ends up in the ocean. Between 4.8 to 12.7 million metric tonnes of plastic waste is estimated to have entered the ocean alone from coastal regions in 2010 [15]. This estimation does not consider other probable sources such as inland regions, ships and etc, so the total number of tonnes per year would be way larger. It is understood that the amount of plastic entering our ocean is far more than the estimates of floating plastic on the surface of the ocean. More than 99% of plastic within our ocean is therefore ‘missing’ [25]. Once it reaches the sea, an interplay of sunlight, wave and wind break down plastic waste into tiny particles, sometimes even less than an inch across. These so-called microplastics are spread throughout the ocean and are found in every corner of the globe. Almost 800 species, including endangered ones, are known to have been affected by plastics.

Since Lagrangian ocean models closely mimic the chaotic nature of the ocean flow, they can be used as data references for ocean plastic transport. If our deep neural network is able to capture its underlying mechanisms, and tell how certain it is in it’s prediction, then it could serve as a great help to stakeholders in finding these plastics in the ocean.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Bayesian Neural Network

Uncertainty estimates are essential in forecasting, decision making, learning from noisy and limited data. The probabilistic approach provides a way to reason about uncertainty and learn from data. There are mainly two kinds of uncertainty one can model, namely aleatoric and epistemic. Aleatoric uncertainty describes the confidence in the input data. It is high when input data is noisy and cannot be reduced by adding more data. Epistemic uncertainty on the other hand describes the confidence of the prediction. It is high when the training data is less. This type of uncertainty can be reduced by adding more data. Epistemic uncertainty is much more challenging than aleatoric as epistemic uncertainty reflects the uncertainty to the model's predictive process [9].

We can estimate this uncertainty using Bayesian neural networks (BNNs) instead of standard neural network (NN). In NNs, weights are assigned as a point estimate or single value. A BNN on the other hand has distribution on the weights w . Instead of point estimate, we have an entire posterior. We first select a likelihood. After that, we select priors over parameters. Then we compute or approximate the posterior of our model and data. Then as provided by [1], the posterior is computed as follows :

$$p(w | X_{train}, y_{train}) = \frac{p(y_{train} | X_{train}, w)p(w)}{p(y_{train} | X_{train})} \quad (2.1)$$

To make a new prediction y_{test} on test data x_{test} and using the training data X_{train}, y_{train} , we do the following:

$$p(y_{test} | x_{test}, y_{train}, X_{train}) = \int p(y_{test} | X_{test}, w)p(w | y_{train}, X_{train})dw \quad (2.2)$$

In equation 2.2, what we are essentially doing is getting a distribution over our prediction. We are sampling our posterior many times randomly, so in summary we are summing over many neural networks with slightly different weights. Therefore, we can think of Bayesian prediction as being a form of ensembling over many models. Unfortunately, exact inference is intractable. Therefore, there's a need to approximate the latent variable we are trying to infer i.e. $p(w | X_{train}, y_{train})$. One of the ways of approximating $p(w | X, y)$ is by using variational inference, where it approximates posterior with a simpler distribution from a variational family of distributions q_θ parameterised by θ . It then minimises the kullback-leibler (KL) divergence [17] between approximate posterior $q_\theta(w)$ and the actual posterior $p(w | X, Y)$ w.r.t θ . It is shown as follows :

$$KL[q_\theta(w) || p(w | X, Y)] = \int q_\theta(w) \log \frac{q_\theta(w)}{p(w | X, Y)} dw \quad (2.3)$$

2.2 Dropout as a Bayesian Approximation

As discussed in section 2.1, it is near impossible to calculate the exact posterior inference, but it can be approximated. To combat this problem, Monte carlo (MC) dropout has been introduced, which uses dropout [22] to compute the uncertainty in the predictions [10]. Dropout is a technique which is applied for solving over-fitting problem in NNs. By randomly dropping out hidden units and their connections during training time hidden units are prevented from co-adapting too much. Assuming that we have a NN with L layers, where W_l, b_l denote the weight matrices, bias vectors of the l th layer, respectively. Then as provided by [10], the objective function using L_2 regularization can be written as

$$\mathcal{L}_{dropout} = \underbrace{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N E(y_i, \hat{y}_i)}_{\text{loss function}} + \underbrace{\lambda \sum_{i=1}^L (\|W_i\|^2 + \|b_i\|^2)}_{L_2 \text{ regularisation with weight decay } \lambda} \quad (2.4)$$

Dropout samples binary variables for each input data and for each layer except the output layer, with the probability p_i for the i th layer, therefore the unit i is dropped if its probability p_i is 0. To update the parameters, same values are used in the backward propagation.

2.3 Recurrent Neural Network

Sequential data like video, language, time series, etc. all show dependence between individual elements across time. NNs treat each data sample separately and hence lose the benefit that can be derived by making use of this sequential information. One way to account for sequential dependency is by joining together a fixed number of consecutive data samples and treat them as a single data point, akin to moving a fixed size sliding window over data stream. One drawback of this approach is that it will always lose the entirety of the time information after the window ends.

Figure 2.1: A standard RNN. Image adapted from [18].

The RNNs are a type of NNs which are suitable for processing sequential data. The figure 2.1 depicts the working of RNN [21] being unfolded into a full network. On the right, we are repeating the same layer structure of network which is on the left side for the complete sequence. At time t , the RNN receives the input x_t and the hidden state from the previous time step s_{t-1} . This hidden state is the memory of the network. Let I be the weight matrix between the input and hidden layers, H be the weight matrix between the hidden states, O be the weight matrix for hidden to output layer. Then current hidden state s_t can be calculated as follows, note that the derivations and equations below are cited and summarized from [12]:

$$s_t = \sigma(Ix_t + Hs_{t-1} + b_s) \quad (2.5)$$

Finally, the output of the network h_t is calculated as follows:

$$h_t = \text{softmax}(O_{s_t} + b_h) \quad (2.6)$$

2.3.1 Types of RNN

The architecture of RNNs can vary depending upon the nature of the tasks. There are mainly four types of RNNs, which are described as follows:

Figure 2.2: Types of RNN. Image taken from [2].

1. **One to one** architecture is the most basic form of Neural network. Here we give the model single input and receive a single output.
2. **One to many** ($T_x = 1, T_y > 1$) architecture is implemented when the situations demands to have multiple outputs for a single input. For example images are classified in multiple classes.
3. **Many to one** ($T_x > 1, T_y = 1$) architecture is used when multiples inputs are needed to provide one output. For example, sequence of images are classified in single class.
4. **Many to many** ($T_x > 1, T_y > 1$) architecture are of two types:
 - (a) ($T_x = T_y$) i.e. The input sequence is equal to the output length.
 - (b) ($T_x \neq T_y$) i.e. Both input and output sequences are of different lengths.

2.3.2 Issues with RNN

The RNNs learns its parameters by using an approach called back-propagation through time (BPTT) [26]. In theory, RNNs can learn long range dependencies over long sequences using BPTT. Unfortunately, this is not the case in reality as they can be difficult to train. It is very well known that the standard RNNs cannot learn dependencies over long intervals [5].

2.3.3 LSTM

The LSTM network [13] is an RNN that overcomes the vanishing gradient problem. As a result, it can be used to learn long range dependencies over long sequences and achieve state-of-the-art results [23],[14]. LSTM networks have memory blocks instead of neurons where a block consists of gates that manage its state and output.

There are three types of gates within a unit which are described as follows, note that the equations below are cited and summarized from [7],

1. **Forget Gate** decides which information should be removed from the block. Let σ be the sigmoid function, h_{t-1} be the output of the previous LSTM block timestep, $t - 1$, W_f be the weight for the forget gate neurons, x_t be the input at current timestep, b_f be the bias for the forget gate. Then, forget gate f_t can be written as

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f) \quad (2.7)$$

2. **Input Gate** decides conditionally what values from the input to update the memory state. Let W_i be the weight for the input gate neurons, h_{t-1} be the output of the previous LSTM block timestep $t - 1$, x_t be the input at current timestep, b_i be the bias for the input gate, h_{t-1} be the output of the previous LSTM block timestep. Then, input gate can be written as

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i) \quad (2.8)$$

\tilde{C}_t be the candidate for cell state at timestamp t ,

$$\tilde{C}_t = \tanh(W_C \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_c) \quad (2.9)$$

To update cell state C_{t-1} to C_t , we multiply C_{t-1} by f_t to forget certain information. After this we add $i_t * \tilde{C}_t$. This results into new cell state

$$C_t = f_t * C_{t-1} + i_t * \tilde{C}_t \quad (2.10)$$

3. **Output Gate** determines which parts of the cell state C_t we will output.

$$o_t = \sigma(W_o[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o) \quad (2.11)$$

4. **Output** is computed by first putting the cell state C_t through \tanh (converts the values to be between -1 and 1) and multiplying it by the output gate o_t .

$$h_t = o_t * \tanh(C_t) \quad (2.12)$$

Figure 2.3: LSTM. Image taken from [7].

2.3.4 GRU

Following the same concept as LSTM, GRU is slightly different, as it has two gates instead of three:

1. **Reset gate**, is used to decide how much of past information should be neglected.
2. **Update gate**, is responsible for determining how much of previous information or prior time steps should be passed to the next state.

GRU have been used to predict vehicle trajectories [6]. In this setting, $[(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)]$ represents a vehicle trajectory consisting of n data points, where data point (x_i, y_i) represents the longitude and latitude coordinates of the vehicle's i^{th} position.

2.4 Convolutional LSTM

The use of LSTM in images results into large number of parameters because the networks are fully connected, and therefore, each pixel in the image needs its own connection. ConvLSTM [27] helps us resolve this issue as it combines LSTM architecture with convolution. This resulting network achieves better performance while significantly decreasing the number of parameters needed to train.

Figure 2.4: Inner structure of ConvLSTM. [28]

The ConvLSTM network is expressed mathematically below, (the derivations and equations below are cited and summarized from [27]):

$$\begin{aligned}
 i_t &= \sigma(W_{xi} * \mathcal{X}_t + W_{hi} * \mathcal{H}_{t-1} + W_{ci} \circ C_{t-1} + b_i) \\
 f_t &= \sigma(W_{xf} * \mathcal{X}_t + W_{hf} * \mathcal{H}_{t-1} + W_{cf} \circ C_{t-1} + b_f) \\
 C_t &= f_t \circ C_{t-1} + i_t \circ \tanh(W_{xc} * \mathcal{X}_t + W_{hc} * \mathcal{H}_{t-1} + b_c) \\
 o_t &= \sigma(W_{xo} * \mathcal{X}_t + W_{ho} * \mathcal{H}_{t-1} + W_{co} \circ C_t + b_o) \\
 \mathcal{H}_t &= o_t \circ \tanh(C_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.13}$$

where '*' represents the convolution operator and \circ denotes the hadamard product.

As with LSTMs, ConvLSTM also has an input gate i_t , hidden state \mathcal{H}_t , forget gate f_t , output gate O_t and cell state C_t . The equations of ConvLSTM networks is similar to the equation of the standard LSTM networks except that the multiplication is replaced with a convolution.

2.5 Concluding remarks

We are estimating uncertainty for trajectory data. As it is a sequence prediction problem and RNNs have shown the ability to learn temporal dependence between observations, we employ this technology. Since our input data is structured like sequence of images and ConvLSTM networks outperforms LSTMs when that is the case, we apply this technique. One of the ways of providing uncertainty in the predictions can be done by BNNs, common NNs only give us point predictions but from theory we find that any common NNs can be considered as a BNN. One of the techniques to do so is by simply keeping the dropout layers active at the testing time (MC dropout). So, we employ this strategy in our research.

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Scope

In this research, we determine how certainty of a neural network's prediction vary as we change our design choices. It is important to establish that prediction accuracy of the model and its uncertainty are two different metrics. Prediction accuracy in our system is measured by the loss function, whereas uncertainty in our case is measured by finding out standard deviation of prediction results per grid cell.

3.2 Data Description

Lagrangian ocean modelling simulations outputs different types of data, such as particle trajectories with spatial coordinates, varying across time. Those can be thought of as tabular data, where each row represents an individual particle with each column being a distinct timestamp t . Furthermore, array-like maps are generate for particle velocities, particle density and particle life expectancy. Particle density is here defined as:

$$\frac{\text{particles count in a grid cell}}{\text{area of the grid}}$$

Life expectancy in a regular grid is a per-cell value of the average age of all particles within that grid cell. Thus, we work with trajectories in a tabular arrangement (see table 3.1 and 3.2) and the other data products in the format of mapped arrays (see table 3.3). Data of this format will be referred to as gridded data from now on. Gridded data have t matrices, having a dimension of $N \times H$ grid cells, where N and H are constant for a particular scenario. The matrix represents the earth, and if we suppose that it has a dimension of 360×720 , then each grid cell has an area of $0.5 \text{ deg} \times 0.5 \text{ deg}$. Similarly, if it has a dimension of 180×360 , then each grid cell has an area of $1 \text{ deg} \times 1 \text{ deg}$.

There are various simulation parameters in Lagrangian ocean modelling which dictates the dimensions of matrices, simulation time, number of particles, grid cell velocities and etc. The different combination of the parameter values results into different scenarios.

Table 3.1: Particle trajectories in X-direction

No. of particles	{	Day 1	Day 2	...	Day t
		32.1	32.1	...	41
		42.1	42.3	...	48
	
		64.3	64.7	...	68
Number of days					

Table 3.2: Particle trajectories in Y-direction

No. of particles	{	Day 1	Day 2	...	Day t
		99.1	99.3	...	99.7
		103.2	103.5	...	107
	
		160.5		...	164.3
Number of days					

Table 3.3: Particle densities in a 360×720 matrix at time t

360	{	10	6	...	1
		4	0	...	1
	
		0	0	...	1
720					

Figure 3.1: This figure depicts **particle trajectories**, notice the green lines in the zoomed-in figure on the right.

Figure 3.2: Particle velocity in Y direction

Fig 3.1,3.2 are a visual representation of velocity, particle trajectory.

3.3 Neural Network Architecture

We opt for a multi-headed architecture, where each independent input series is handled by a separate NN and the output of each of these models is combined before giving a prediction. This architecture helps us take advantage of the multivariate data available.

To achieve uncertainty in the prediction, we apply MC dropout at every weight layer at both train and test times.

The architecture is depicted in figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Bayesian ConvLSTM component

Figure 3.4: Multi-headed Bayesian ConvLSTM

3.3.1 Type of ConvLSTM

We use many-to-one and many-to-many ConvLSTMs in our research. In many-to-one ConvLSTM, we predict one step ahead given n prior inputs. Using this prediction as input, we predict the next-following time step and so forth. This allow us to predict a chosen number of timesteps ahead. Equation 3.1 explains how we subsequently predict more than just one step ahead in time, where f is the transformation function, p_t is the predicted value for the next time $t - 1$. This predicted value p_t is used to predict p_{t+1} and so on. o are the observations.

$$\begin{aligned} p_t &= f(o_{t-1}, o_{t-2}, \dots, o_{t-n}) \\ p_{t+1} &= f(p_t, o_{t-1}, \dots, o_{t-n-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

Many-to-many ConvLSTMs are capable of predicting the entire forecast at once. See equation 3.2 for it's mathematical interpretation.

$$p_t, p_{t+1} = f(o_{t-1}, o_{t-2}, \dots, o_{t-n}) \quad (3.2)$$

3.4 Preprocessing

3.4.1 Sampling

The data provided to us have global distribution of particles and our goal is the local estimation of particle distributions over time i.e. where do particles that come from and which areas do those particles move to. This is an issue as our network doesn't track individual particles because it doesn't predict particle positions. It predicts particle densities, which is an accumulated value per grid cell. We overcome this issue by limiting the prediction to focus just on the particles we want to track by only working with the particles within a certain user-defined area. Limiting the particles to a given local area means that we need to sample the original set of particle trajectories, filtering out particles with an origin location outside of our region-of-interest.

The algorithm for sampling proceeds as follows:

1. Select the position and the size of the bounding box for a scenario.
2. Store the trajectories of all the particles that are inside the bounding box from t_0 till t_n .
3. Convert those trajectories into t_n gridded data of dimension 360×720
4. Reduce the matrices dimensions such that its width and height is of the maximum distance particles have travelled horizontally and vertically.
5. Repeat the above steps for every scenario and store the dimensions of the reduced matrices.
6. Convert all the different scenarios of possible different dimensions into the same dimension, which is the maximum dimension size of all the scenarios through padding with 0s. We will refer to this dataset as gridded particle count data.
7. Gridded velocity data is processed so that they have the same dimension as of gridded particle data.

We perform step 6) of the sampling algorithm mostly to reduce the dimensions of our input, as this will significantly decrease the network parameters.

We convert the (directional) velocity to velocity magnitude (i.e. speed) as follows:

$$s = \sqrt{u^2 + v^2}$$

and extract the direction by using this formula:

$$\alpha = \arctan\left(\frac{v}{u}\right)$$

The reason of doing so is explained in the section 3.4.2.

Figure 3.5: **Overview of sampling process**, the first step describes the selection of the particles inside the bounding box (red box), the second step shows the particles position at the end of a scenario's duration. Third step shows the cropping process where we keep only the relevant part of the gridded data (as described in the step 4 of the sampling algorithm). Fourth step describes the padding process (as described in the step 6 of the sampling algorithm)

3.4.2 Normalization

In order to normalise our multivariate dataset, we take some inspiration from how image data is normalised. Let p_i be the pixel value of a cell, p_{min} be the minimum pixel value and p_{max} be the

maximum pixel value, then normalising p_i can be formulated as

$$p_n = \frac{p_i - p_{min}}{p_{max} - p_{min}} \quad (3.3)$$

We use the same approach to normalise our dataset. Although it is not as straight forward as normalizing the image, since the maximum (usually 255) and minimum pixel (0) values are readily known.

For normalising particle density, let pc be the number of particles in a particular grid cell, pc_{min}, pc_{max} be the minimum and maximum number of particles inside the grid of all our dataset respectively, then normalised particle density can be written as

$$pc_n = \frac{pc - pc_{min}}{pc_{max} - pc_{min}} \quad (3.4)$$

As mentioned in section 3.4.1, we convert the (directional) velocity to velocity magnitude and direction. It is mainly done to counter an issue which was seen while normalising velocity. The velocity is a signed-value number (i.e. contains positive and negative value ranges), therefore after normalising velocities to a range of 0 to 1, land particles (particles on land), which had 0 velocity, were having a value of approximately 0.5. This might limit the neural network in finding correlation between the velocity and how particle count change in a gridcell. The normalisation process of magnitude velocity and direction seem far more intuitive, therefore we follow this approach. Let ps be the speed of a grid cell, ps_{min}, ps_{max} be the minimum and maximum speed of a grid cell of all our dataset respectively, then magnitude velocity can be written as

$$ps_n = \frac{ps - ps_{min}}{ps_{max} - ps_{min}} \quad (3.5)$$

The direction data albeit like velocity is a vector, meaning it also contains positive and negative value ranges, it can be easily converted to only positive values by adding the direction values by 360 deg (direction values range from -360 deg to 360 deg).

$$pd_n = \frac{pd - pd_{min}}{pd_{max} - pd_{min}} \quad (3.6)$$

3.5 Uncertainty Quantification

In section 2.2, we discuss how dropout can be seen as a Bayesian approximation. The MC dropout is also used at test time, making predictions no longer deterministic, it rather depends upon which nodes are randomly chosen. Therefore, given the same input data, the model predicts different values each time. We run the model 100 times for each input sequence and get 100 different prediction results. The μ and its σ is computed for each grid cell. For 100 different results, we check how many grid cells lie within $\mu - \sigma$ and $\mu + \sigma$. In summary, one grid cell of the confidence map represents the number of times the predicted value of the grid cell has lied between one standard deviation. We refer to this interpretation of uncertainty in our results as confidence maps.

Figure 3.6: In **Confidence Maps**, a grid cell colored blue means around 28 to 36 times out of 100, the predicted grid cell has had a value in the range of one standard deviation

Chapter 4

Experiments and Results

The network is trained on 44 different scenarios. Each scenario (367 timesteps) is converted into 355 sequences (15620 sequences in total) i.e. the network has a lookback of 6, a lookahead of 6 (for a many-to-many network), each frame having a dimension of $100 \times 140 \times 1$. The model is tested on a different scenario. The network has three input heads, each input head has two convLSTM2D layers of 32 filters each with a kernel size of 2×2 and 2×2 respectively, a MC dropout layer between each convLSTM layer with a drop rate of 0.4 and a Conv3D layer at the end with 8 filters. These three networks get merged using concatenate layer and at the end a Conv3D layer is applied with 1 filter. We train the prediction model with RMSprop optimizer using a learning rate of .001. Training is done for 10 epochs with early stopping. We use pixel-wise Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss function for training.

4.1 Effects on uncertainty with number of particles in a grid

In this experiment, we compare how a model behaves when it is given just one grid cell versus when it is given more than one grid cell. The grid cells in both the scenarios contain one particle each. The position of the bounding box is the same for both the case, which essentially means that the velocity of the grid cells in both the scenarios are similar. The purpose of this experiment is to see how the prediction of a grid cell is affected by its neighboring grid cells and whether the number of grid cells have any impact on the certainty in the prediction. I expect that the model will be much more certain in the former scenario than the latter. The results for one grid cell is given below. The input sequence (see figure 4.1) have input frames from t_n, t_{n+1}, t_{n+2} in the first row and $t_{n+3}, t_{n+4}, t_{n+5}$ in the second, output sequence (see figure 4.2) have ground truth frames from $t_{n+6}, t_{n+7}, t_{n+8}$ in the first row and $t_{n+9}, t_{n+10}, t_{n+11}$ in second row.

Figure 4.1: Input sequence

Figure 4.2: Ground truth sequence

Figure 4.3: Prediction sequence

Figure 4.4: Confidence maps

From the results, we find that the model struggles with correctly predicting grid cell's density (see figure 4.3). The difference in order of magnitude between ground truth and the result is almost of 10. This can be due to the used normalisation strategy. Density of the predicted results appear to be decreasing for the initial prediction time steps. For only a single grid cell the confidence map (see figure 4.4) is having a lot of contenders for the probable position of the grid cells.

Figure 4.5: Prediction error graph

The difference between ground truth and predicted results can also be visualized using prediction error box plot (see figure 4.5), where we compute MSE loss for 100 different predictions for each day. This is another way of showing confidence in our predictions. Here we see that error loss has a relatively wide range per time step considering the simple nature of the input sequence. Now we look at the scenario where there are more than two grid cells.

Figure 4.6: Input sequence

Figure 4.7: Ground truth sequence

Figure 4.8: Prediction sequence

Figure 4.9: Confidence maps

In this scenario, all of the three grid cells have different velocities. The grid cell on far right (see figure 4.6) showed no movement for the entire input sequence and hence that translated into little to no movement in the prediction sequence (see figure 4.8) for that grid cell. The grid cell in the middle moved the most of the three and the prediction seemed to convey that. The discrepancy between the predicted and the ground truth's density seems to remain the same as with the former scenario. Our model seems to recognise different movements of individual grid cells i.e. the movement of one cell does not seem to influence the other. By looking at the confidence maps of both the scenarios, the certainty of the model does not seem to be effected with the number of grid cells in the input sequence.

4.2 Effects on uncertainty in regions of turbulent flows

In the earlier experiment, we tested our model with the simplest of inputs, it's complexity was only restricted to finding the trajectory of the grid cell. Now we see how the model performs when it is given a relatively complex input sequence where some grid cells have more than one particle, so the model has to also deal with dissipation (one grid cell dissipating into two or more grid cells). We have selected the region of the bounding box which has grid cells with relatively higher velocities. I expect to see a noticeable increase in the uncertainty in those regions of the grid where grid cells have showed a complicated behaviour (rapid grid cells movements, one grid cell dispersing into many grid cells) across successive time steps.

Figure 4.10: Input sequence

Figure 4.11: Ground truth sequence

Figure 4.12: Prediction sequence

Figure 4.13: Confidence maps

The predicted result (see figure 4.12) seem to be blurry for certain grid cells, especially those

that have shown fast movements in the successive times steps. The confidence map seems to deviate from what was expected. The model seems to be more certain for this input sequence than it was for experiment 4.1. It has relatively higher number of cells colored in green (confidence ranging between approx. 40-60%) but more often than not in the wrong positions when compared with the ground truth (see figure 4.11).

4.3 Effects of input interpolation function on certainty

In this experiment we test whether the network m_s trained on scenarios produced by a fixed set of parameters perform better than the network m_v trained on scenarios produced by variable set of parameters (i.e. same network which we used to perform the above experiments). The m_s is trained on 4970 scenarios (355×14 scenarios), for 6 epochs with early stopping. I expect m_s to perform better than m_v as the dataset will have lesser variability which might help the model to predict better.

Figure 4.14: Input sequence

Figure 4.15: Ground truth sequence

From the results in figure 4.16, we see that there's a noticeable difference in the scale of both the predictions. The maximum grid cell value for m_s is around 0.8 and around 1.25 for m_v . In a qualitative perspective, as can be seen in figure 4.18, m_v performs better than m_s . This can be indicative of better predictions of the densities by m_v for the corresponding cells. When prediction graphs of both m_v and m_s are placed side-by-side, we can notice a similar trend in how the error changes across the time steps. The difference between the confidence maps of both the models can also be seen in figure 4.17, confidence map from m_v seems to be more widespread (number of grid cells predicted for a certain grid cell) than m_s , which represents that it is more certain about its predictions.

It can be due to the fact that m_v is trained on a much bigger dataset (approx. 3 times). This experiment might be skewed in favour of m_v due to this large discrepancy in the amount of training data but there is no denying the fact that having a large dataset is very important in our research.

Figure 4.16: The first prediction sequence is from m_s , below is the output from m_v

Figure 4.17: Confidence maps

Figure 4.18: Prediction error graphs, Left: m_s Right: m_v

Chapter 5

Discussion

The results indicate that changing design choices seems to have an effect on the model's confidence. We tested our model with different input sequences to test how it will react. The model seemed to react differently in different scenarios, i.e. in experiment 4.1 and 4.2, as we increased the input's complexity, the model behaved differently as the confidence maps seemed to more widespread meaning for predicting the density for a single grid cell, relatively larger number of grid cells were chosen as contenders.

There is a certain degree of blurriness associated with our prediction results. The degree of the blurriness depends upon how the grid cells are moving i.e. if the grid cells are moving rapidly across time steps then the blurriness is larger than when they are moving slower. This can be largely due to the loss function used [20]. If we break down our research problem into a simpler problem, then we are predicting the trajectory of the grid cell given n set of input sequences. As the grid cells (consider grid cell with only particle for simplicity sake) can move in any direction, it leads to uncertainty. The way the loss function gets about this is by averaging out all the probable cases where the grid cell can go. This might be the reason as to why there is a big difference in densities between the predicted results and the ground truth, as the prediction seems to divide the particles across many grid cell. This can also be the reason as to why the confidence map seemed to more spread out for the complex input sequences. Several studies have analyzed the impact of loss functions in video predictions [3],[29]. Earlier results showed that when mean absolute error (MAE) was used instead of MSE, then the predicted cells had densities in the range of the ground truth values. The downside is that the predicted results did not seem to acknowledge isolated grid cells which were away from the cluster of grid cells of non-zero values (Non-adjacent non-zero grid cells). When MSE was used, the results had all the grid cells with non zero values (whether a grid cell was isolated or not). This again highlights the importance of the choice of loss function in our research.

From our earlier results, I found that the type of architecture used also seems to have a major impact on the predictions. It was observed that when we used many-to-one architecture, the prediction results were almost identical with what the grid cell values were in the last time step of input sequence. The only difference was that some grid cells with non-zero values disappeared. The model in this case seems to learn that only the state of grid cell values in the last time step of the sequence is relevant for the predictions and grid cell movements were seen as disappearing grid cells. This can largely be attributed to the way grid cell values moves across the time. This interpolation by the network can be due to the little difference between the two successive time steps. The model fails to learn the whole phenomenon, i.e a connection between values lost by grid cell gained by the neighbouring grid cells. The many-to-many architecture has a completely different output. Here, a visible movement (or rather change in the densities) of the predicted grid cells are seen across the time steps. Only the grid cells which are not moving in the predicted results seem to remain stationary.

As discussed above, the reasoning of the blurriness is due to the uncertainty. The prediction space for a grid cell is large and we can seem to decrease this by adding context. There are certain

ways by which we can look to do so. Firstly, we can increase the input sequence length, which by itself should be long enough to capture the phenomenon. From the experiments, it is seen that the grid cells that show little to no movements remain stationary in the predicted results. A larger input sequence can seem help the model in gauging the underlying phenomenon. This also presents us with a dilemma. In our earlier results, when the input sequence was longer (e.g 10), the predicted results suffered. Possibly as we increase the input sequence length, it also increases the input parameters and with it comes the input noise, which resulted in distorted prediction values. Therefore, we really need to find an optimum length for the input sequence.

As seen from the experiment 4.3, having a higher variability in our dataset results in better predictions. We can look at ways in which we can increase the variability in our dataset by training our models on regions having grid cells with different velocities, which might help the model to learn the correlation between the changing grid cell's particle densities with speed and direction. This in turn will also give more context to the network, thereby further decreasing the prediction space.

Bibliography

- [1] Moloud Abdar, Farhad Pourpanah, Sadiq Hussain, Dana Rezazadegan, Li Liu, Mohammad Ghavamzadeh, Paul Fieguth, Xiaochun Cao, Abbas Khosravi, U Rajendra Acharya, et al. A review of uncertainty quantification in deep learning: Techniques, applications and challenges. *Information Fusion*, 2021. 3
- [2] Andrej Karpathy blog. The unreasonable effectiveness of recurrent neural networks, 2015. [Online; accessed October 28, 2021], see figure number 1. 5
- [3] Mohammad Babaeizadeh, Chelsea Finn, Dumitru Erhan, Roy H Campbell, and Sergey Levine. Stochastic variational video prediction. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1710.11252*, 2017. 25
- [4] David Barber. *Bayesian reasoning and machine learning*. Cambridge University Press, 2012. 1
- [5] Yoshua Bengio, Patrice Simard, and Paolo Frasconi. Learning long-term dependencies with gradient descent is difficult. *IEEE transactions on neural networks*, 5(2):157–166, 1994. 5
- [6] Seongjin Choi, Hwasoo Yeo, and Jiwon Kim. Network-wide vehicle trajectory prediction in urban traffic networks using deep learning. *Transportation Research Record*, 2672(45):173–184, 2018. 7
- [7] colah’s blog. Understanding lstm networks, 2015. [Online; accessed October 28, 2021], see figure number 6. 5, 6
- [8] Philippe Delandmeter and Erik van Sebille. The parcels v2. 0 lagrangian framework: new field interpolation schemes. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 12(8):3571–3584, 2019. 1
- [9] Armen Der Kiureghian and Ove Ditlevsen. Aleatory or epistemic? does it matter? *Structural safety*, 31(2):105–112, 2009. 3
- [10] Yarín Gal and Zoubin Ghahramani. Dropout as a bayesian approximation: Representing model uncertainty in deep learning. In *international conference on machine learning*, pages 1050–1059. PMLR, 2016. 4
- [11] John Cristian Borges Gamboa. Deep learning for time-series analysis. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1701.01887*, 2017. 1
- [12] Ian Goodfellow, Yoshua Bengio, and Aaron Courville. *Deep learning*. MIT press, 2016. 4
- [13] Sepp Hochreiter and Jürgen Schmidhuber. Long short-term memory. *Neural computation*, 9(8):1735–1780, 1997. 5
- [14] Zhiheng Huang, Wei Xu, and Kai Yu. Bidirectional lstm-crf models for sequence tagging. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1508.01991*, 2015. 5
- [15] Jenna R Jambeck, Roland Geyer, Chris Wilcox, Theodore R Siegler, Miriam Perryman, Anthony Andrady, Ramani Narayan, and Kara Lavender Law. Plastic waste inputs from land into the ocean. *Science*, 347(6223):768–771, 2015. 2

- [16] Alex Krizhevsky, Ilya Sutskever, and Geoffrey E Hinton. Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 25:1097–1105, 2012. 1
- [17] Solomon Kullback and Richard A Leibler. On information and sufficiency. *The annals of mathematical statistics*, 22(1):79–86, 1951. 3
- [18] Yann LeCun, Yoshua Bengio, and Geoffrey Hinton. Deep learning. *nature*, 521(7553):436–444, 2015. 4
- [19] Yann LeCun, Bernhard Boser, John S Denker, Donnie Henderson, Richard E Howard, Wayne Hubbard, and Lawrence D Jackel. Backpropagation applied to handwritten zip code recognition. *Neural computation*, 1(4):541–551, 1989. 1
- [20] Sergiu Oprea, Pablo Martinez-Gonzalez, Alberto Garcia-Garcia, John Alejandro Castro-Vargas, Sergio Orts-Escolano, Jose Garcia-Rodriguez, and Antonis Argyros. A review on deep learning techniques for video prediction. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 2020. 25
- [21] David E Rumelhart, Geoffrey E Hinton, and Ronald J Williams. Learning representations by back-propagating errors. *nature*, 323(6088):533–536, 1986. 4
- [22] Nitish Srivastava, Geoffrey Hinton, Alex Krizhevsky, Ilya Sutskever, and Ruslan Salakhutdinov. Dropout: a simple way to prevent neural networks from overfitting. *The journal of machine learning research*, 15(1):1929–1958, 2014. 4
- [23] Nitish Srivastava, Elman Mansimov, and Ruslan Salakhutdinov. Unsupervised learning of video representations using lstms. In *International conference on machine learning*, pages 843–852. PMLR, 2015. 5
- [24] Erik Van Sebille, Stephen M Griffies, Ryan Abernathey, Thomas P Adams, Pavel Berloff, Arne Biastoch, Bruno Blanke, Eric P Chassignet, Yu Cheng, Colin J Cotter, et al. Lagrangian ocean analysis: Fundamentals and practices. *Ocean Modelling*, 121:49–75, 2018. 1
- [25] Erik Van Sebille, Chris Wilcox, Laurent Lebreton, Nikolai Maximenko, Britta Denise Hardesty, Jan A Van Franeker, Marcus Eriksen, David Siegel, Francois Galgani, and Kara Lavender Law. A global inventory of small floating plastic debris. *Environmental Research Letters*, 10(12):124006, 2015. 2
- [26] Paul J Werbos. Backpropagation through time: what it does and how to do it. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 78(10):1550–1560, 1990. 5
- [27] SHI Xingjian, Zhouong Chen, Hao Wang, Dit-Yan Yeung, Wai-Kin Wong, and Wang-chun Woo. Convolutional lstm network: A machine learning approach for precipitation nowcasting. In *Advances in neural information processing systems*, pages 802–810, 2015. 7
- [28] Zhuoning Yuan, Xun Zhou, and Tianbao Yang. Hetero-convlstm: A deep learning approach to traffic accident prediction on heterogeneous spatio-temporal data. *Proceedings of the 24th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery & Data Mining*, 2018. 7
- [29] Hang Zhao, Orazio Gallo, Iuri Frosio, and Jan Kautz. Loss functions for image restoration with neural networks. *IEEE Transactions on computational imaging*, 3(1):47–57, 2016. 25